

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Rice remains from Neolithic Age excavated in China

Tang Shengxiang, China National Rice Research Institute, Hangzhou 310006, China

China is one of the first countries in which rice was farmed. One hundred nine Neolithic remains of rice culture in China, dating back to 1050-5850 BC, have been studied. Carbonated grains were most commonly excavated.

Forty-nine of the samples date to 1050-2550 BC, 43 to 2550-4050 BC, and 17 to 4050-5850 BC. Eighty-two of the remains, including the three oldest at Luojiajiao, Hemudu, and Pengtoushan, were discovered in the middle and lower basins of the Yangtze River (see figure).

Thousands of carbonated whole grains, leaves, and stems were found in

Hemudu. Based on length, width and shape of grains, and characteristics of awns, the grains were identified as cultivated indicas and japonicas and a few types of wild rice (*O. rufipogon* Griff). In Luojiajiao, the grains originated from japonicas.

Many carbonated grains and hulls were discovered in unearthed pottery in Pengtoushan. Some scientists think these are grains of cultivated rice.

Based on these findings, rice farming may have been developed as long as 8,500 years ago in the middle and lower basins of the Yangtze River. ■

Distribution of excavated rice remains from the Neolithic Age in China.

Breeding methods

Effect of seedling age on flowering of cytoplasmic male sterile and restorer lines of rice

G. Bassi, A. Rang, and D. P. Joshi, Seed Science and Technology Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, Punjab, India

Nonsynchronized flowering of parental lines, unavailable area-specific seed production technology, and difficulty in arranging adequate isolation make hybrid rice seed production challenging. We manipulated seedling age of some cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) and restorer lines (prospective parents of promising hybrids) to synchronize flowering.

Four CMS and eight restorer lines were studied during 1992 wet season. The nursery was transplanted when seedlings were 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, and 45 d old. Data were recorded at initiation of panicle emergence, 50% flowering, and complete flowering. Days to flowering were calculated from transplanting date.

Seedling age affects panicle emergence in both CMS and restorer lines (see figure). Panicle emergence tended to be delayed in the 20- and 25-d-old seedlings but was quicker in those 35-45 d old. In general, panicle emergence was advanced or delayed by half the number of days difference in seedling age compared with a 30-d-old seedling. Data at panicle emergence correlated with those at 50% flowering and complete flowering.

In genotypes IR58025 A, IR13292 R, PAU1106-21-3 R, and PAU1106-21-4 R, panicle emergence was delayed or advanced by as many days as there was difference between seedling age and a 30-d-old seedling. Genetic differences among genotypes in the ability of seedlings to establish after transplanting, might cause this difference in panicle emergence. ■

Deviation in days to panicle emergence

Genetics of fertility restoration of wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterile lines in rice

P. K. Singh, R. Thakur, and V. K. Chaudhary, Plant Breeding Department, Rajendra Agricultural University, Bihar, Pusa (Samastipur) 848125, India

Thirteen elite rice cultivars were crossed with cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines V20 A, IR54752 A, and IR58025 A. Pusa 33, IET6148, Pankaj, Rajshree, and TCA48 were identified as effective restorers based on seed and pollen fertility of the F_1 s.

Only six testcrosses had more than 90% seed and pollen fertility in F_1 . The F_2 progeny of these were analyzed for inheritance of fertility restoration (see

table). On the basis of percent seed set, F_2 plants were grouped as fertile (above 80% seed fertility), partially fertile (20-80% fertility), and sterile (below 20% seed fertility).

Two fertility restoration genes, Rf_1 and Rf_2 , are known in rice. Two independent dominant genes govern seed fertility restoration ability of Pankaj and Rajshree; a single dominant gene governs restoration in Pusa 33.

The mode of action of the two genes varied in the four crosses. The F_2 population of V20 A/Rajshree, IR58025 A/Rajshree, and IR58025 A/Pankaj segregated into a 9-6-1 ratio, revealing epistasis with incomplete dominance. V20 A/Pankaj showed dominant epistasis (12:3:1). V20 A/Pusa 33 and IR58025 A/Pusa 33 showed monogenic segregation (see table).

Segregation for fertility restoration in F_2 populations of some crosses. Cuttack Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, 1991 rabi season.

Cross	F_1 seed fertility (%)	F_1 pollen fertility (%)	F_2 plants (no.)	Segregation for seed fertility ^a			Expected segregation ratio	χ^2
				F	PF	S		
V20 A/Rajshree	92	93	154	92	54	8	9:6:1	0.85
V20 A/Pusa 33	92	93	163	116	-	46	3:1	0.99
V20 A/Pankaj	90	91	130	94	26	10	12:3:1	0.67
IR58025 A/Rajshree	91	94	174	101	61	12	9:6:1	0.49
IR58025 A/Pusa 33	94	96	180	142	-	38	3:1	1.45
IR58025 A/Pankaj	92	93	121	72	39	10	9:6:1	1.91

^aF = fertile (above 80% fertility), PF = partially fertile (20-80% fertility); S = sterile (below 20% fertility).

In Pankaj and Rajshree, Rf_1 had a stronger effect on fertility restoration than did Rf_2 . Fertility restoration was high when both dominant alleles (Rf_1 , Rf_2) were present. It was less pronounced when only Rf_1 was present, and was further reduced (partial fertility) when only Rf_2 was present. The double recessive genotype ($rf_1rf_1rf_2rf_2$) did not restore fertility. Only one dominant restorer gene ($RfRf$) was found in Pusa 33.

Variation in seed fertility restoration indicates these genes have different penetrance and are affected by modifiers. ■

Restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile lines derived from MS577 A

S. Leena Kumary, M. Mahadevappa, and A. Mohan Rao, Genetics and Plant Breeding Department, University of Agricultural Sciences, GKVK, Bangalore 560065, India

Several stable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines (Pushpa A, Mangala A, ES18 A, and Intan Mutant A) developed in Karnataka carry MS577 A cytoplasm and have good agronomic traits. They could not be used directly to develop hybrids, however, because good restorers were not available. We successfully identified effective restorers for them.

We crossed the CMS lines with improved varieties and cultures and obtained 115 F_1 s at the Main Research Station, Hebbal, during 1992 dry season. Hybrids and their parents were transplanted during 1992 wet season in rows of 30 plants spaced at 15 × 20 cm. Ten plants from each hybrid were labeled. Three panicles from each plant were marked and then bagged before flowering. Spikelet fertility was calculated as percentage of filled grains.

Florets from the upper part of the panicles were collected before flowering and stained with 1% acetocarmine for pollen fertility studies. Pollens classified as fertile were fully developed, round, and stained deeply.

Individual plants were classified as fertile, partially fertile, and sterile based on pollen and spikelet fertility. Pollen